

COPERNICUS RESPONDING TO EU CITIES MISSION

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Editorial

by Nektarios Chrysoulakis

It is with great pleasure that we launch the first issue of the CLMS-Cities Newsletter. This project brings together leading research institutions, European agencies, commercial partners and city stakeholders to develop innovative ways of monitoring and understanding urban CO₂ emissions. By harnessing the power of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) and more Earth Observation data, our aim is to equip European cities with actionable data and tools to accelerate their journey toward climate neutrality.

In this issue, you will discover how the project is shaping its emissions model, engaging with the EU Mission Cities and other stakeholders, and co-creating solutions with a broad user base. We invite you to follow our progress, join the dialogue, and in turn help us ensure that CLMS-Cities contributes to a more sustainable urban future.

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by Zina Mitraka

As climate change continues to reshape the global agenda, cities have emerged as both a significant source of emissions and a key focus for mitigation. Around 70% of global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions are linked to the energy needs of urban populations, and a large portion of these emissions are generated within city boundaries (Scope 1 emissions). Addressing this challenge requires more than commitment without direction. It demands actionable data, innovative tools, and targeted strategies that cities can use to plan and measure their transition to net-zero.

CLMS-Cities is designed to support cities on their path toward climate neutrality by harnessing the power of Earth Observation (EO) and the [Copernicus Land Monitoring Service \(CLMS\)](#). We aim to provide cities with spatially disaggregated, locally relevant information on urban CO₂ emissions and sequestration, helping urban planners, decision-makers, and local stakeholders design more effective mitigation strategies and understand their city's emission patterns.

The CLMS-Cities Mission for Urban Climate Action

The core objective of CLMS-Cities is to explore how CLMS can be used to better understand and quantify urban carbon dynamics at the local scale, supported by other Copernicus datasets and input from third-party sources. Despite the small area of cities, their complex mix of buildings, infrastructure, mobility, and green spaces makes them simultaneously interesting environments for advancing methods for CO₂ emissions monitoring.

To address this challenge, CLMS-Cities combines EO data with satellite imagery, mobility datasets, building inventories, and vegetation indices. This integrated approach enables the modelling of carbon emissions and sinks across Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) such as those from the [CLMS Urban Atlas](#).

The model CLMS-Cities will provide high-resolution emissions maps, which through co-design with users, will be translated into area relevant CO₂ profiles, to support urban planners, policymakers, and stakeholders in making informed, climate-focused decisions across sectors.

Innovation at the core

CLMS-Cities pushes the boundaries of what is currently possible in urban CO₂ emissions monitoring, proposing a new approach to enhance CLMS with urban emissions and sinks. The long-standing challenge of urban environmental data fragmentation is tackled exploiting Copernicus allowing comparisons between cities, laying a groundwork for future improvements in emissions inventories and analysis in a regular update-cycle.

A Vision for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities

The ambition of CLMS-Cities goes well beyond technical innovation. It seeks to redefine how EO data can support urban climate strategies, offering reliable, consistent, and scalable insights that empower local governments to act. By embedding CO2 information into urban planning datasets, such as those found in the CLMS Urban Atlas, the project opens the door to integrating climate objectives into everyday planning decisions.

This vision is aligned with the [EU Cities Mission](#), which challenges cities to reach net-zero emissions by 2030. However, the journey to climate neutrality is complex, and cities need the right tools to make informed choices. Whether it is evaluating the CO2 impact of a new transit corridor, identifying high-emission zones, or calculating the carbon benefits of increased urban greenery, CLMS-Cities provides the intelligence to guide those decisions.

Project Objectives

Improving urban CO2 modelling at local scale by combining the [CURE method](#) and the [SUEWS model](#) to generate a unified modelling framework, i.e. the CLMS-Cities CO2 emission model and evaluate its outcomes against flux tower eddy covariance CO2 observations.

Contributing to CLMS evolution by a proof-of-concept demonstration of the constructive utilization of CLMS in urban CO2 monitoring, by developing a new modular and scalable product chain, fusing CLMS data with relevant Copernicus products, time series of Copernicus Sentinels observations and third party data (urban mobility), to provide tangible results (urban CO2 emission information at local scale) to be integrated in CLMS (new products), offering new dimensions and new interests for Copernicus Land products.

Demonstrating the technical and operational feasibility of enhanced CLMS, to provide the EU Mission Cities community with spatially disaggregated environmental intelligence and benchmark data for evaluating Green House Gases (GHG) inventories in cities, extending the so far limited uptake of CLMS products into land planning decisions related to climate change mitigation and supporting cities to meet the EU Mission Cities ambitious objectives.

Demonstrating the feasibility of CLMS-Cities to replicate its method to the first ten Mission Label Cities, delivering consistent products across the EU Mission Cities and strengthening the readiness for an operational deployment by developing a strategy for integrating these products in a standard way in CLMS in the future, based on appropriate interaction with the European Environment Agency (EEA), the Entrusted Entity of CLMS.

CLMS-Cities represents a step change in how we use Earth Observation to inform urban emissions monitoring by transforming Copernicus data into actionable knowledge, that empower cities to reach climate neutrality

Building capacity and awareness-raising concerning the new CLMS products through organization of effective communication/dissemination to enhance the use of CLMS across cities and human settlements (4th engagement priority of [GEO - Group of Earth Observations](#)), contributing to the objectives of the GEO post-2025 strategy for exploiting Earth Intelligence in managing the multi-dimensional nature of urban sustainability.

CLMS-Cities CO2 Emissions Model Concept

by Robert Spirig

A modular CO2 emissions model is being developed to offer detailed, spatially-explicit insights at 10 m resolution into the scope 1 (local) urban CO2 sources and sinks since these can be influenced directly by cities themselves. By combining satellite-derived data from CLMS and the Urban Atlas, the model will capture emissions from five key sectors: Industrial emissions, mobility, building emissions, AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use), and Human Respiration (often neglected but substantial in an urban environment and in evaluations against measurement).

The city of Vitoria-Gasteiz in Spain serves as the first case study as it participates in the EU Mission. Here, model outputs will be validated against eddy covariance flux tower measurements and the official city carbon inventory from the Climate City Contract. Following this pilot and the gained insights, the model is to be scaled to ten additional European Union Mission Cities in a second step with benchmarking it against the local emission inventories. The ultimate goal is to lay a solid groundwork for the eventual scaling to all EU mission cities in an effort of EEA/Copernicus to support EU Mission Cities to reach climate neutrality in the near future as the model can help policy makers and urban planners with its high spatial and temporal resolution to determine hot spots, diurnal and seasonal dynamics.

With the CLMS Urban Atlas at its center the model output can be tied easily to its update frequency, ensuring that our results remain relevant and can also provide progress over time, because carbon emissions need to be monitored and tracked over time regularly. This itself is a complex task but even harder at a city level as not all emissions to consider take place in the city. Since CLMS-Cities focuses on the in-boundary emissions (Scope 1) however, cities can directly understand and derive actionable insights from our model. As we incorporate local data and local emissions as much as feasible.

Ultimately, we strive to supplement traditional city inventories that often rely on aggregated annual data with temporally and spatially resolved outputs. Such granularity enables the cities to better understand not just how much CO2 is being emitted, but where and when — a critical advancement for designing targeted mitigation strategies and timing them to reach maximum effect now and in the future.

Sectoral Breakdown

Mobility

primarily includes the movement of cars as main emitters. With GPS, the movement of individual cars can be captured at high temporal resolution and analyses statistically for specific street segments with the use of transport network data like OSM. While the initial dataset is biased towards users that participate in GPS data recording, a calibration with full traffic counts ensures better representativeness. With this calibrated dataset, emission modelling via SUMO will be conducted to arrive at CO2 estimates for individual road network segments. Weekly and diurnal cycles can also help in a later stage to potentially derive dynamic population (see human respiration).

Industrial emissions

of scope 1 tend to be point sources within the city bounds that are reported in national registries based on legislation and open data initiatives throughout Europe. We incorporate the annual emissions from industrial point sources based on national registries whenever available. These yearly values are then scaled down to hourly/weekly profiles with the use of either EDGAR or COCO2 emissions database and benchmarked with the climate city contracts.

Building Emissions

entails the emissions from residential, commercial and institutional buildings. These will be calculated based on building height/volume, energy use profiles, and heating technologies (e.g. district heating vs oil/gas heating). The driver for the emissions will be the heating/cooling activity based on temperature as provided from ERA5-Land data.

AFOLU

is (usually) the only sector that includes not only sources (e.g. plant respiration), but also a sink (via photosynthesis) by the vegetation. We will model the two process rates of based on various input layers (LAI, NDVI and others) and the land cover type (CLCplus backbone layer) of CLMS for different types of vegetation. Since the native resolution of Sentinel is 10m urban green is often partially masked as single trees are mixed with other surface types in the same pixel. We will strive to run the model with a 1m resolution for AFOLU to account for and better capture even smaller green patches in the urban environment and thus determine net CO2 exchange from urban parks, forests, and surrounding agricultural areas in great detail.

Human Respiration

is often overlooked as a CO2 source but it is still an important and non-negligible source of CO2 in dense urban environments with high population. The model integrates demographic data, activity patterns either from GPS data or from literature together with metabolic rates to estimate respiration-related emissions on a per-pixel basis in an effort to represent this source.

Case Studies: Testing CLMS-Cities Across Europe

CLMS-Cities has originally selected ten pioneering European cities, winners of the EU Mission Cities Label 2023, as its case studies: Vitoria-Gasteiz, Sønderborg, Mannheim, Madrid, Valencia, Valladolid, Zaragoza, Klagenfurt, Cluj-Napoca, and Stockholm. The EU Mission Cities Label is awarded to cities that have developed credible Climate City Contracts, that are both action plans and investment strategies to achieve climate neutrality by 2030.

The CLMS-Cities model will be developed and tested in Vitoria-Gasteiz, the project's Tier 1 city and full consortium partner. Vitoria-Gasteiz will also host a new flux tower to validate the CO2 emissions modelling. The model will then be applied to additional Tier 2 cities, demonstrating its transferability and scalability. While the initial plan was to test the method with the cities that first received the EU Mission Cities Label, we now consider to include more cities, since all EU Mission Cities have reached greater maturity in their climate planning processes and have formalized their Climate City Contracts.

Ultimately, CLMS-Cities aims to provide a method for all EU Mission Cities with reliable, benchmark data to refine their climate strategies, contributing to more evidence-based planning and supporting Europe's path toward climate neutrality.

Vitoria-Gasteiz: An EU Mission City Leading by Example

by Beatriz García-Moncó Piñeiro

Vitoria-Gasteiz stands out as one of the first EU Mission Cities to secure the Mission Label, recognizing its robust Climate City Contract and commitment to climate neutrality by 2030. With a proven track record in emissions reduction and sustainable urban planning, the city provides an ideal testbed for CLMS-Cities. Its strong governance, community involvement, and dual participation in both the Climate Neutral and Adaptation Missions make it a key partner, ensuring that project outcomes are both scientifically rigorous and practically relevant for European cities.

Working for and with Cities

by Zaheer Khan

At the heart of CLMS-Cities is a simple idea: the project will only succeed if it is designed with and for cities. To make this possible, we have developed an interactive framework that brings together data providers, scientists, and urban stakeholders in a process of continuous exchange.

From the start, the project launched stakeholder workshops to capture the real needs of cities and the [European Environment Agency \(EEA\)](#) in carbon emissions monitoring. These sessions aim to shape how urban CO2 emissions can be best assessed through the CLMS Urban Atlas within CLMS-Cities.

The process follows the Collaborative Requirements Engineering and Stakeholder Engagement (CoReS) method, combining workshops with interviews and online surveys. This ensures that voices from Tier 1 and Tier 2 Mission Label Cities are heard, while Tier 3 cities are welcome to contribute through wider engagement.

Through workshops, consultations, and co-creation activities, users guide the definition of CLMS-Cities products, test outputs, and help refine results.

This continuous dialogue ensures that CLMS-Cities does not just produce data, but it delivers actionable knowledge that cities can directly apply in their journey towards climate neutrality.

First Stakeholders Workshop: Start Building Dialogue

by Katy Kampour

On 30 June 2025, CLMS-Cities hosted its 1st Stakeholders Workshop, organised online by the University of the West of England (UWE), Bristol. The event marked an important step in co-creating the project with its users and partners.

The workshop brought together around 20 representatives from a diverse range of organisations, including academic institutions, European and international agencies (EEA, ESA), innovation and city networks (Climate Alliance, Climate-KIC, Covenant of Mayors, NetZeroCities), private-sector data providers, and representatives from Mission Cities such as Vitoria-Gasteiz.

Discussions were structured around two interactive roundtables. The first explored data challenges and methods, focusing on how urban CO2 inventories can be improved by integrating EO and local datasets. The second focused on urban planning and policy, examining how emissions data can support city decision-making and climate strategies.

The workshop highlighted the value of bringing together technical experts, city practitioners, and European agencies in a collaborative forum. The insights gathered will guide the further development of the CLMS-Cities model and prepare the ground for upcoming workshops and demonstration events.

Frenchay campus at UWE Bristol. Photograph: UWE Bristol. Source: The Guardian.

Project Activities

Over the past months, the CLMS-Cities team has already been actively engaging with key European events to present and promote the project's vision.

EU Cities Mission Conference, Vilnius (6–8 May 2025): At this invitation-only flagship event hosted under the theme *“Harnessing City Successes: Advancing Climate Action for 2030”* the CLMS-Cities booth and consortium representatives engaged with over 900 participants, including city officials, EU bodies, and innovation networks.

CLMS General Assembly, Krakow (19–22 May 2025): The project featured a presentation and participated in a fishbowl discussion during the assembly, fostering dialogue with the Copernicus community and reinforcing its integration into CLMS evolution.

EU Space Days 2025, Gdańsk (27–28 May): CLMS-Cities was spotlighted in a HaDEA-organized panel on EU projects, positioning the initiative among Europe's forefront space-enabled climate innovations.

R&I for a Competitive Green Transition Conference (23–24 June 2025): The team presented CLMS-Cities to R&I and green innovation audiences, advancing the project's visibility among key industry and academic stakeholders.

ESA Living Planet Symposium, Vienna (23–27 June 2025): Held under the theme *“From Observation to Climate Action and Sustainability for Earth,”* this premier Earth Observation symposium featured CLMS-Cities contributions among global scientific and policy exchanges

All activities of the CLMS-Cities project are available through the project's web-site: <https://clms-cities.eu/news.html>.

CLMS-Cities

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